

USE OF AUTOMATED INTERACTIVE WORKSHEETS CREATED USING WIZER.ME IN TEACHING THE DISCIPLINE "FINANCE"

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8035661>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 06th June 2023
Accepted: 13th June 2023
Online: 14th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Education, distance learning, pedagogical technologies, information and communication technologies, electronic resource, automated interactive worksheet, Wizer.me service, interactive exercises.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the main directions of reforms in the higher education system, requirements for teachers in terms of information and communication competence, possibilities of using the Wizer.me service, provides practical examples of creation of automated interactive worksheet on the discipline "Finance".

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a wide range of measures is being taken to improve the quality of training of highly qualified personnel, the development of human capital in accordance with the requirements of the labor market, the gradual increase in the level of enrollment in higher education, the gradual introduction of international standards into the process of training staff. In order to introduce digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, the following activities are being implemented in our country [1]:

- organization of a system for training highly qualified engineering and technical personnel for the requirements of the digital economy;
- creation of additional conditions for the continuous development of professional skills of teaching staff;
- individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, the development of distance learning services, the widespread introduction of webinar technologies, online, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" into practice;
- organization of distance learning programs based on modern information and communication technologies;
- widespread introduction of a system of electronic libraries with the possibility of distant use of them;
- acceleration of the creation of national electronic educational resources;
- organization of work on the translation of foreign electronic educational resources necessary for the training of national personnel;
- development of the use of modern software products in the educational process.

Teachers of higher educational institutions should be proficient in modern information and communication technologies, including knowledge, skills and abilities: [2-8]:

- to type texts, prepare tables and draw pictures in various programs, including Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel. The teacher should be able to use these programs in the preparation of educational and methodological complexes, writing textbooks, manuals, scientific articles, abstracts of reports at conferences, conducting lectures and seminars;
- to be able to present the main content of the educational material in the form of presentations in various programs, including Microsoft Power Point;
- to find important information and to use content of various educational Internet sites;
- to have the skills to search and work with large volumes of data using special software;
- to be able to use official data and other information posted on the websites of state authorities and administration, including statistical data and analytical reports;
- to use the materials of the National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan www.lex.uz, read the content of legal documents governing the use of information and communication technologies in all areas, including the higher education system;
- to work with modern educational environments, including the modular object-oriented dynamic control environment Moodle and other systems;
- to be able to develop electronic training courses for use in various educational environments, structure the educational material, compose questions, tests, assignments, control the work of students.

One of the online services that help develop automated interactive worksheets in various disciplines is Wizer.me. The Wizer.me service is in English and differs from others in that it includes a set of interactive exercises arranged in the form of a sheet that can be presented in Russian, English and other languages. When creating interactive sheets, teachers master the skills of organizing independent work, creating various types of exercises using an online service, working with video and audio information in sheets, using information processing methods (analysis, synthesis, classification, ordering, systematization) to present it in the Wizer.me environment, which characterizes their level of development of information competence. The Wizer.me service has positive aspects: interactivity as the ability to organize network interaction using online technologies, accessibility, free service, combination and variety of exercises in interactive sheets.

Figure 1 shows the various interactive exercises that can be done in the service.

Figure 1. Types of exercises in the service the Wizer.me service

Let's discuss one example of one automated interactive worksheet in the discipline "Finance", prepared on the theme "Essence and types of money funds".

At the beginning of the interactive worksheet is written the title of the theme that the students are to study. Further, theoretical material on this theme is presented in brief form. Several interactive exercises aimed at testing knowledge are given after the theoretical part.

Figure 2 shows the example of the "Matching" exercise. This exercise allows you to create the correlation of any two elements. This exercise uses terms from the category "Economic entities" and the corresponding terms for each of them from the category "Money funds". Students should select one economic entity and determine which money fund corresponds to that entity.

Figure 2. Example of the interactive exercise "Matching"

Figure 3 shows an example of the interactive exercise "Classification". Students must classify all the terms in the picture between the two categories "Centralised money funds" and "Decentralised money funds". Each term should be rearranged to the appropriate category.

Find centralized and decentralized money funds

Figure 3. Example of the interactive exercise “Classification”

Figure 3 shows an example of the interactive exercise “Word Search Puzzle”. Word Search Puzzle is a word search puzzle, but it only works with Latin words. The students should find words like enterprise, household, expenses, finance, deficit, income, budget, money, fund, and debt in a box consisting of various jumbled letters.

Find the main financial terms

To mark a word click its first letter then click its last.

J	D	L	D	S	A	M	O	N	E	Y	D	Words: ENTERPRISE HOUSEHOLD EXPENSES FINANCE DEFICIT INCOME BUDGET MONEY FUND DEBT
K	C	O	D	E	F	I	C	I	T	F	Q	
U	I	N	C	O	M	E	D	E	B	T	E	
G	P	C	J	E	X	P	E	N	S	E	S	
H	O	U	S	E	H	O	L	D	D	N	N	
F	I	N	A	N	C	E	F	U	N	D	N	
F	O	B	U	D	G	E	T	B	T	B	V	
V	B	E	N	T	E	R	P	R	I	S	E	

Figure 4. Example of the interactive exercise “Word Search Puzzle”

Wizer.me is a simple and fast tool for creating automated interactive worksheets with tasks and exercises. The platform provides unique opportunities for preparing tasks for working with various tasks, is interesting and easy to use, contains many tools. The teacher can choose any kind of interactive exercise, add video, images, audio recordings, tables, text.

The creation of automated interactive sheets in the Wizer.me service encourages teachers to create interesting interactive exercises for students, use new information and communication technologies in the process of organizing independent work, improve their digital literacy and the level of professional competence.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-5847 from 8 October 2019 "On Approval of the Concept of Development of the System of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" // National Database of Legislation, 03/18/2022, No. 06/22/89/0227 [in Russian].
2. Akhunova Ye. A. (2016). The main activities of teachers of higher educational institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Problems of modern science and education. No. 14 (56). pp. 117-119 [in Russian].
3. Akhunova Ye. A. (2016). The use of information and communication technologies as one of the factors for improving the efficiency of teachers of higher educational institutions // Problems of modern science and education. No. 1 (43). pp. 209-211 [in Russian].
4. Akhunova Ye. A. (2015). Different approaches to the development of the structure of an electronic training course in the Moodle environment // Science, education and culture. No. 2 (2). pp. 26-28 [in Russian].
5. Akhunova Ye. A. (2015). The main stages of the teacher's activity in the process of developing and using an electronic training course // Science, technology and education. No. 10 (16). pp. 188-190 [in Russian].
6. Akhunova Ye. A. (2015). Fundamentals of the application of modern information and communication technologies in the organization of independent work of students. Bulletin of science and education. No. 9 (11). pp. 70-72 [in Russian].
7. Akhunova Ye. A. (2016). Basic requirements for the use of modern information and communication technologies by teachers of higher educational institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Problems of modern science and education. No. 36 (78). pp. 80-82 [in Russian].
8. Akhunova Ye. A. (2020). Modern requirements for teachers of higher educational institutions in the field of using modern information and communication technologies // International Journal of the Humanities and Natural Sciences. No. 6-1(45). pp. 66-68 [in Russian].
9. Golovnya D. A. (2016). Possibilities of using the Wizer information platform. Me in teaching literature // Innovative technologies in mechanical engineering, education and economics. Vol. 2, No. 2(2). pp. 76-78 [in Russian].
10. Tabachuk N. P. (2017). Service WIZER.me as a means of developing information competence of students // Modern trends in the development of science and technology. No. 1-9. pp. 114-116 [in Russian].
11. Kornyt'ska Yu. (2021). Flipped ESP class: a solution for developing reading skills // Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science. no. 54-4. P. 16-22 [in Russian].
12. Malkova T. V., Baranov A. Yu. (2022). Organization of independent work of students with the help of modern digital tools // Questions of Pedagogy. No. 3-2. pp. 121-124 [in Russian].

13. Richter T.V., Abramova I.V. (2021). The use of digital educational resources in the study of programming at the university // Karelian scientific journal. T. 10, No. 2(35). pp. 22-24 [in Russian].
14. Gorlova E. A., Zhuravleva O. V. (2023). The use of services for the preparation of worksheets in modern teaching practice // Modern problems of science and education. No. 1. S. 49 [in Russian].